

MAGNETIC STUDY OF METAL DERIVATIVES OF 1:3- β -DIKETONE.
PART II

BY SAGAR MEHTA AND D. M. DESAI

The diamagnetic susceptibilities of seven metal chelates of benzoylacetone, namely, Be, Mg, Zn, Cd, Ca, Sr and Ba, have been determined by a modified form of Gouy's balance. The results show the absence of singlet structure in these chelates as all the compounds studied are found to be diamagnetic. The fair agreement between the observed and the calculated values of molar susceptibilities of these chelates, with the exception of cadmium, suggests that in these chelates there is no systematic and appreciable diamagnetic contribution of metal chelate bonds. The replacement of CH_3 group by C_6H_5 group has no abnormal effect on the diamagnetism of these compounds.

In continuation of the work reported earlier (this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 189) the diamagnetic susceptibility of metal derivatives of benzoylacetone of the second group metals has been studied in this investigation. It appears from the literature that the magnetic study of not a single metal derivative of benzoylacetone has been reported so far.

EXPERIMENTAL

The metal chelates of benzoylacetone, namely Be, Mg, Zn, Cd, Hg, Ca, Sr and Ba benzoylacetates, were prepared by the known methods using benzoylacetone of Merck's quality and inorganic salts of very high purity. Benzoylacetone was twice distilled in a glass-joint apparatus before use. The compounds so prepared were carefully purified by repeated crystallisations and dried before measurement. The purity of the compounds was determined by the melting point and the metal content, by chemical analysis.

The diamagnetic susceptibilities of these compounds were determined by a modified form of Gouy's balance and the susceptibility values were calculated by using the equation (cf. Angus and Tilston, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1947, 53, 235),

$$\chi = \frac{a}{w} \frac{F + C}{w}$$

as described previously (*loc. cit.*). The results of these measurements are shown in Table I in which χ_s represents the specific susceptibility values and χ , their molar susceptibilities. The susceptibility values recorded in the table are the mean of at least three independent determinations and these have been expressed in terms of $\cdot 1 \times 10^{-6}$ c.g.s. units.

TABLE I

Benzoyl acetates.	M. W.	χ_a .	χ_M	
			Obs.	Calc.
Be	331.36	0.556	184.20	183.01
Mg	346.66	0.555	192.40	185.55
Zn	387.72	0.511	198.10	198.11
Cd	434.75	0.460	200.00	216.60
Hg*	..	...	...	...
Ca	362.42	0.525	190.30	193.08
Sr	409.97	0.495	203.20	202.85
Ba	459.70	0.451	207.30	214.25

* This compound was found to decompose during the preparation.

Structure of Metal Benzoylacetates.—All the compounds studied in this investigation were found to be diamagnetic. Although the theory of singlet structure has been discarded for normal and stable compounds, yet it may be inferred from the magnetic study of these metal chelates, that they do not have a singlet structure as suggested by Sudgen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 318) because if these chelates had single electron linkages, they would have shown an overwhelming paramagnetism. The structure of these metal chelates of benzoylacetone like that of the metal chelates of acetylacetone is therefore represented as one involving single and double bonds in the following manner.

Comparison of Molar Susceptibilities.—The molar susceptibilities of these metal chelates have been calculated by using the susceptibility value of benzoylacetone ion and Angus' values (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1932, 136A, 569) of metal ions. The susceptibility value of benzoylacetone ion has been computed in a similar manner (cf. acetylacetone ion) by making use of Pascal's constants (cf. Bhatnagar and Mathur, "Principles and Application of Magnetochemistry", p. 138) for various atoms and constitutive correction constants and has been found to be -91.33×10^{-6} . The observed and the calculated values of the molar susceptibilities are recorded for the purpose of comparison in the last two columns of Table I.

It is seen that the observed values of molar susceptibility of all the metal chelates of benzoylacetone, except that of cadmium, agree fairly well with those calculated by using Angus' values of metal ions; a slight departure from the observed values is, however, expected as Angus' values for metal ions used in the calculation are for free ions. The fair agreement between the observed and the calculated values of molar susceptibilities, except in the case of cadmium, would indicate that there is no systematic and appreciable diamagnetic contribution due to metal chelate bonds in these complexes. These results apparently support the observation made in the previous investigation (*loc. cit.*) and are also in agreement with the conclusion reached by Hutchisson and Elliott (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1948, 16, 920) in the study of thorium acetylacetone.

Effect of Chelating Group on M-O Bonds.—The structure of metal chelates of acetylacetone and benzoylacetone may, in general, be represented as shown below :

(where M is the metal ion)

In the case of acetylacetonates the two groups R' and R'' are the same (R' and R'' = Me) while in the benzoylacetoneates the two groups R' and R'' are different (R' = Me and R'' = Ph). It is interesting to find out whether the M-O bonds in both acetylacetonate and benzoylacetoneate are of the same character or there is any deformation in the case of benzoylacetoneate, where there is no symmetry and where the two groups R' and R'' are different, that is, on one side there is a Me group and on the other there is a phenyl ring.

The computed values for the benzoylacetoneate ion and acetylacetonate ion are 91.33 and 50.95 respectively. Hence, the difference between the susceptibility of the two radicals comes out to be 40.38 which corresponds to the diamagnetic contribution of C_5H_5 . Similarly, the difference between the benzoylacetoneate and acetylacetonate of a particular metal chelate was found out and the average diamagnetic contribution for C_5H_5 group was obtained. This is shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Metal.	χ_M values		Difference. C_5H_5
	Acetylacetonate.	Benzoylacetoneate.	
Be	107.5	184.2	76.7
Mg	106.3	192.4	86.1
Zn	121.6	198.1	76.5
Cd	121.4	200.0	78.6
Ca	113.2	190.3	77.1
Sr	127.7	203.2	75.5
Ba	130.9	207.3	76.4
			Average 78.13

It is seen from the above table that except in the case of Mg, there is a close agreement in the difference obtained between the two sets of values. The average difference

which corresponds to the diamagnetic contribution of C_6H_6 , comes out to be 39.06 which is in fair agreement with the value obtained from the computed values of the two radicals. These results indicate that in such compounds the replacement of CH_3 group by C_6H_5 group has no abnormal effect on the diamagnetism of these compounds. This conclusion is supported by the work of Kohavec and Kohlrausch (*Ber.*, 1940, 73B, 1304) who have observed from the study of the Raman spectra of several such compounds that in these chelates the two $M-O$ bonds are practically identical, even when R' and R'' are different.

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INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BOMBAY.

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